

Sample 05a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0033
	{Ca}	26.7
	{Fe}	18.5
	{Si, Ca HiP}	9.9
	{Al, Ca}	8.4
	{Si}	5.8
	{Ca, Fe}	5.5
	{S, Ca}	3.9
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.7
	{Al, Si}	2.4
	{Si, S, Ca}	2.3
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.8
	{Mg, Fe}	1.7
	{Si, Fe}	1.0
	{Mg, Ca}	0.9
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.8
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.8
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Mg}	0.7
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.6
	{Mg, Si}	0.6
	{Al}	0.6
	{Al, Si, K}	0.4
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{S, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Al, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Mn}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Al}	0.1
	{Mn, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	14.4
Pellet	1.6
Ore preparation undifferentiated	8.2
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.2
Ore / hot metal	1.2
BOF converter slag	25.7
BOF converter slag slopping	3.1
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.8
Desulph slag	0.6
Ca-aluminate slag	8.4
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.8
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	8.5
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.4
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.3
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.2
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.3
Coal and cokes or soil	2.6
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	3.5
Carbon rich - other	6.5
Cement or BOF converter	3.1
Cement	0.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.2
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	2.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	5.0
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	1.2

141 μm

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	24.4
Site - ore / hot metal	1.2
Site - slag	39.6
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.8
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	8.5
Site - flux / refractory	0.4
Site - refractory	0.5
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.3
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	2.6
Site - carbon-rich other	3.5
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	6.5
Urban; rarely site - slag	3.1
Urban	0.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	2.0
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	5.0
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	1.2

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 05b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0019
	{Ca}	28.0
	{Fe}	18.2
	{Si, Ca HiP}	9.7
	{Al, Ca}	7.4
	{Si}	7.0
	{Ca, Fe}	6.0
	{S, Ca}	3.9
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.7
	{Si, S, Ca}	2.3
	{Al, Si}	2.1
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.6
	{Mg, Fe}	1.5
	{Si, Fe}	0.9
	{Mg, Ca}	0.9
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.8
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.7
	{Mg}	0.7
	{Al}	0.6
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Si}	0.3
	{Al, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{S, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Si, K}	0.1
	{Mn}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	12.1
Pellet	2.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	5.5
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	1.8
BOF converter slag	26.5
BOF converter slag slopping	2.7
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.3
Desulph slag	0.8
Ca-aluminate slag	6.3
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.1
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	10.4
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.3
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.4
Coal and cokes or soil	2.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	5.7
Carbon rich - other	10.4
Cement or BOF converter	1.5
Cement	0.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.4
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	2.4
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	4.3
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.1
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.7

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	19.6
Site - ore / hot metal	1.8
Site - slag	37.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.1
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.2
Site - flux / slag	10.4
Site - flux / refractory	0.3
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.4
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	2.8
Site - carbon-rich other	5.7
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	10.4
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.5
Urban	0.7
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	2.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	4.3
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.1
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.7

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 05c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0059
{Ca}	23.2
{Fe}	20.7
{Si, Ca HiP}	9.4
{Si}	9.3
{Al, Ca}	7.5
{Ca, Fe}	5.6
{S, Ca}	3.5
{Si, Ca LoP}	2.8
{Al, Si}	2.3
{Si, S, Ca}	2.2
{Mg, Fe}	1.7
{Si, Fe}	1.5
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.3
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.9
{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.7
{Al}	0.7
{Al, S, Ca}	0.6
{Mg, Ca}	0.6
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.6
{Mg, Si}	0.5
{Mg}	0.5
{Mg, S, Ca}	0.4
{Al, Ca, Fe}	0.3
{Al, Si, K}	0.3
{Mg, Al, Si, K}	0.3
{S, Ca, Fe}	0.2
{Mg, Al, Ca}	0.2
{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.2
{Si, P, Ca}	0.2
{Mg, Si, S, Ca}	0.1
{Na, Al, Si}	0.1
{Mn, Fe}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	12.8
Pellet	4.8
Ore preparation undifferentiated	7.5
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.2
Ore / hot metal	2.3
BOF converter slag	23.1
BOF converter slag slopping	2.4
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.5
Desulph slag	0.4
Ca-aluminate slag	6.3
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	5.9
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.2
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.4
Coal and cokes or soil	4.4
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	4.4
Carbon rich - other	7.4
Cement or BOF converter	2.0
Cement	0.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.1
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	3.2
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	6.9
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.3
Apatite	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.3
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	1.3

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	25.2
Site - ore / hot metal	2.3
Site - slag	34.8
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	5.9
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.2
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.4
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	4.4
Site - carbon-rich other	4.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	7.4
Urban, rarely site - slag	2.0
Urban	0.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	3.2
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	6.9
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.4
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	1.3

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels